

TWO UNDESCRIBED SPECIES OF *APLOSPORELLA* SPEG.

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ABSTRACT

During a mycological survey on the coelomycetous fungi of Amravati (Maharashtra), two new species of *Aplosporella* spg. were collected at different parts of Amravati, growing saprophytically on dead leaves of *Citrus karna* Raf. and dead stems of *Thuja orientalis* Linn. For its diagnosis and specific identify the fungi were studied in detail with respect to morphology and dimensions of various fruiting structures. Further, they were also compared with other known species of *Aplosporella*, including the type species *A. chlorostroma* Speg and found differ in the size of pycnostroma and conidia. Hence, described here as a new species.

Key words : *Aplosporella*, new species

Aplosporella is a genus of fungi in the family Botryosphaeriaceae. During a mycological survey on the coelomycetous fungi of Amravati (Maharashtra), two new species of *Aplosporella* Speg. (Spegazzini, 1880) were collected at different parts of Amravati, growing saprophytically on dead leaves of *Citrus karna* Raf. and dead stems of *Thuja orientalis* Linn. For its diagnosis and specific identify the fungi were studied in detail with respect to morphology and dimensions of various fruiting structures. Further, they were also compared with other known species of *Aplosporella*, including the type species *A. chlorostroma* Speg. (Spegazzini, 1880) and found differ in the size of pycnostroma and conidia. Hence, described here as a new species The specimens examined and deposited in the herbarium of 'Ajrekar Mycological Herbarium', Agharkar Research Institute, Pune (India). The detailed description of the same with latin diagnoses are as follows.

1. *Aplosporella citrae* sp nov. (Figure- 1)

Pycnostroma dark, unilocular, ostiolate, immersed, nearly globose, measure 112 – 180 x 120 – 200 μ m; conidiophores simple, short, 4 – 12 μ m long; conidia dark – brown, oval to oblong, one – celled, measure 18 – 30 x 10 x 16 μ m; sterile hairs present.

Pyonostroma atra, unilocularia, immersa, globosa, magnit 112 - 180 x 120 – 200 μ m; conidiophora simplicia, brevia, 4 – 12 μ m long; conidia fusca – brinnea, ovoidia vel oblonga, unicellularia, magnit 18 – 30 x 10 – 16 μ m; hyphis sterilis numerosis.

The specimen collected from Amravati on dried leaves of *Citrus karna* Raf. (Rutaceae) on 10 – 07 – 2001, legit. P.S. Kaste, No. AMH 8840, holotypus.

The present collection was found to be distinct in all morphological characters and dimensions from *A. hesperidica* Speg. (Subhedar, 1977)

being collected on a host of the family Rutaceae (viz *Feronia elephantum* Corr.) Therefore, it is presented here as a new taxon.

Figure-1: *Aplosporella citrae* sp.nov.

a) pycnostroma, v.s.

b) conidia

2. *Aplosporella coniferae* sp. nov (Figure-2):

Pyonostroma erumpent, dark – brown, ostiolate, measure 0.43–0.68x0.78– 1.6 mm, multiloculate, irregularly arranged, measure 120–148x80 – 160 µm, conidiophores simple, short, hyaline, measure 12–20x1.2–2 µm, conidia oval to oblong, dark – brown, smooth, one – celled, measure 16–24x10 –14 µm; sterile hairs present.

Figure-2: *A. coniferae* sp.nov.

a) pycnostroma, v.s.

b) conidia

Pycnostroma erumpentia, fusca – brunnea, ostiolata, magnit. 0.43–0.68x0.78–1.6 mm, multilocularia, irregularia, magnit 120 – 148 x 80 – 160 µm; conidiophora simplicia, brevia,

hyalina, magnit. 12 – 20 x 1.2 x 2 µm; conidia ovoidia vel oblonga, fusca – brunnea, unicellularia, magnit. 16 – 24 x 10 – 14 µm; hyphis sterilis numerosis.

The specimen was collected from Amravati on dead stems of *Thuja orientalis* Linn. (Cupressaceae) on 07 – 11 – 2000, legit, P.S. Kaste, No. AMH 8841, holotypus.

The present species is distinct in morphology from *A. thujae* Pet. (Petraik and Sydow, 1927) described on the same host *Thuja orientalis* Linn. It is also distinct from *A ephedricola* Ahmad (Ahmad, 1969) described on *Ephedra foliata*.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am thankful to Principal and Head, Department of Botany, Adarsha Mahavidyalaya, Dhamangaon – Rly for providing necessary laboratory facilities and encouragement.

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DOI:<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7198225>

Received: 19 January 2014;

Accepted; 27 February 2014;

Available online : 12 March 2014